

Playing the Design Game

Defining and processing tacit knowledge in a board game publishing company

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Abstract: This article discusses how designers learn about the creation of board games by familiarizing themselves with tacit knowledge and company processes. To some extent board game design depends on general design methodology and knowledge. However, in order to be able to work in an international board game publishing house and to design board games (and thus facilitate play) for a multicultural audience, the designer has to know about preferences regarding materials, production processes, visualization and packaging. A board game is usually a product of teamwork where designers from different fields of expertise come together to solve design challenges having to do with both form and function. Since a board game sometimes is created from the idea to a ready made product all set for marketing inside a game publishing house, the designer also has to understand the different stages of the product development process.

This study is conducted in the department of product development at a Scandinavian game publishing house with professional board game designers coming from different educational backgrounds. The designers are of different ages and in different stages of their careers. Traditional research methods such as qualitative thematic interviews are used to demonstrate how tacit knowledge is transferred by both management and fellow designers and how a designer becomes familiar with the company's design philosophy. The findings are that expertise in game design involves mastering a multitask challenge which may best be learned through familiarizing oneself with both tacit knowledge learned in everyday work but also by analyzing feedback coming from different sources.

Key words: *Game designer, board game, game publisher, tacit knowledge, design philosophy*

1. Introducing games

Games are a universal part of the human experience, for all cultures, genders and ages. To play games is one of the most basic activities in human life. Playing games is about experiencing them. Board games are products which deliver genuine experiences and encounters, sought by the consumers of today. Games involve players and role playing. Games can be played as individuals or with teams. Games have rules. Depending on the game idea, they involve varying degrees of skill and strategy.

Games involve competition – a game is either won or lost. Nevertheless, the most important part of playing does not seem to be winning the game as much as the playing itself. This means that there is a constant need for games that provide the players with fresh and memorable gaming experiences.

The game business of today can be seen as a duality of classical board games in one end and new technology games in the other. In between stand so called hybrid games with elements from both traditional and digital games. Traditional board games may quite easily be taken from one media into another without the rules or the gaming experience suffering from this change [1]. As Juul puts it, games are a transmedial phenomenon [2].

2. Traditional games as part of the content industry

Board games have been said to live a renaissance during the first years of the 21st century. Although many board games are now available as computer games, the traditional board game is still a popular means of gathering friends and family around a table to enjoy each others company while playing. Playing board games has grown in popularity in all Scandinavian countries even though computer and console game playing are becoming more important activities all the time. Even the economic recession is considered as a somewhat beneficial phenomenon for board game companies, as people are spending more time at home.

Zimmerman sees the game industry structured like any other content industry – it consists of producers, publishers and distributors and its endemic problems have mainly to do with technology, economics and culture [3].

Game companies of today aim to produce games that have potential of becoming long lived products. A game company, or a publisher of games may bring out a maximum of some 30-40 novelties out on the market each year. These games have been selected out of hundreds of game ideas worked up by professional game inventors, game designers inside the companies, other game publishers or even everyday people. Every game company wants to create products which have the potential to become long-lived hits on the market. However, coming up with a hit product or a classic game is for the players to decide. The life cycles of games have become rather short.

Interesting games may not last on the market more than 2 or 3 years, whereas real golden eggs can live up to many decennia. From a game company's perspective it may take from 6 months up to one and a half years to develop a game idea from scratch to a ready made product, depending on the visuals, components and textual content.

The two strongest mass-market board game cultures in the Western world are the German and Anglo-American gaming cultures. German board games are seen as real “gamer's games” with their high quality components, artistic visual materials and high complexity levels in their game mechanics. Some of the gamers see the German games as designer board games as they often have more tactical and strategic depth with a focus on the mechanism compared to world-widely marketed mass-produced games. The Scandinavian game market consists of game products from local game publishers as well as Anglo-American and Central-European board games.

3. Designing the experience of play

Generally, the industrial designer usually has an idea about what the designed product is about to express. The producer moves the idea into production and at the same time includes some material or technical aspects to it. The product may develop an internal meaning that the designer has not consciously meant to include in it. The receiver of the product attaches her own meaning to it which may be something very different from what has been the aspiration of the designer. Nevertheless, the designer has made the occurrence of this meaning possible [4].

As games are designed products, the role of the game designer is fundamental in the creation of games. A game publishing house cannot function without cooperation with game designers, may they work inside the company or as freelancers. Which special issues, approaches, and ways of thinking do game designers need to become familiar with to be able to work for a game publisher? A game designer needs a way to analyze games, to try to understand what works and what makes a game interesting. The clue in designing games is the ability to combine interesting thematic ideas with exciting mechanics – the ways to play a game. In other words game design is about creating systems of playing. Thus, a game designer is an architect of systems and more importantly, an architect of the experience of play. In a summary, creating games requires both an understanding of the craft of game design as well as an appreciation for the ways in which games are played in the real world.

The product development department at a game publishing house can thus be seen as a playfield of tacit knowledge, where a seamless cooperation between different professionals enables the creation of interesting and good-quality board game novelties.

Polanyi's notion on tacit knowledge is simple: According to this definition we may know more than we can tell [5]. Nonaka and Takeuchi's view on knowledge is that it is, before all, something that is tacit – not easy to see or to communicate. Tacit knowledge is personal and difficult structure and thus hard to share with others [6]. A successful game development process requires that tacit knowledge is both utilized and shared with colleagues. Nevertheless, the subjective and intuitive character of tacit knowledge makes it hard to transfer elsewhere in the organization. Therefore, tacit knowledge must be formulated into words or numbers that everyone may understand. Organisational knowledge is created at the moment when tacit knowledge becomes explicit, and then back to tacit again [7].

The game design process starts with answering the question: Why do I want to design this game? To whom am I designing this game is the next question and there are some more, as suggested by Ellington, Addinal and Percival: Is there a space on the market for this kind of game, does it have enough novelty value? What kind of game will it be? What materials does the game require?[8] Game design work at a publishing company means that even further questions are posed, as will be illustrated in the following.

4. What it means to design a game

Making a game is a design activity. To design something is to give that something a visual form and structure. Designing something is to communicate significance through visual appearance. A design project starts with initiation, continues with exploration and results in preliminary design and development of a product. For new products with fresh features, the design process is directly initiated by creative thinking. Design is also about

solving a problem, a process the designer is involved in as soon as he or she confronts the possibilities of the potential end-product [9].

How are board games designed? What are the tasks of a game designer? What kind of a creative process is demanded so that a board game is refined from an idea to a ready made game all set for publishing?

A game designer is the person responsible for developing a game concept into a game product. A game designer is thus not necessarily the inventor of the game idea, but an architect who defines every aspect of a game, from how it looks to how it will be produced. It is essential for the game designer to understand that he or she is creating an experience. Coming up with an idea for a game is not hard. Building and refining this idea into a playable game is the challenge. At a game publishing house, this challenge often is solved on in a team.

A game is a collection of parts which interact with each other often in complex ways. In other words, a game is a system. The game designer is the designer of the gaming activity. Salen and Zimmerman therefore identify creating a game as a second-order design. Interaction cannot be designed, but rather the artifacts and rules that encourage or discourage the interaction in games [10].

Designing a board game in its concrete form includes the designing of the board, defining the nature of the playing pieces and how they can be moved across the board. It also includes determining the procedures by which players are allocated or acquire tokens, the relationship between movement on the board and any other aspects of play and the nature and role of any ancillary playing materials [11].

Like any other designer, the game designer very seldom is a lonely wolf. He or she works with and for other people. A product development group is a beneficial environment to work for a game designer. From the team an individual game designer gains the access to different viewpoints against which game ideas and their visual form can be tested and questioned.

5. Designers and publishers as creators of games

The game designers of today are almost without exception coming from the backgrounds of computing, social sciences and visual arts. In other words, there is not yet an educational program in the academic field that would purely offer studies in board game design. Thus, the product development team will most probably consist of designers with different kind of theoretical and practical knowledge.

Learning to design games cannot only consist of a purely theoretical approach. As Salen and Zimmerman say, designers learn best through the process of design – directly experiencing the things they make [12]. This methodological approach is called iterative design and it is a cyclic process that alternates between prototyping, play testing, evaluation and refinement. The working methods of a product development team in a game publishing company illustrate well the iterative design process.

Even though one single person may get credit for a novel idea, it is hard to imagine that this idea could have been born without peer support. A single idea cannot be connected with a single person within the group because ideas are not important before they have been elaborated on, re-intrepreted and put in use by others [13].

Group dynamics and an active discussion about game products in development within the product development team helps tacit knowledge to be communicated further at a game publishing house. In Sawyer's view there are

even more benefits to active communication between colleagues: A lively discussion is an activity that creates flow at its best. The discussion leads to flow, which again leads to more creative thinking [14].

6. Defining the design process

The most important tools for a game designer are his or her own creative mind, openness to ideas and different kinds of stimulus offered by everyday life. However, it is no longer enough for a board game to have a brilliant idea and a refined working mechanism. The creator of a game, just like the creator of any product of the content industry, also needs to take into consideration its target audience and marketing potential in each step of the design process.

According to previous studies [15], a game publisher has three alternative ways of developing games: 1) By developing a ready made game idea (mechanics) of a professional game inventor into a ready made product, 2) by adapting a ready made game into the own cultural context or finally 3) starting from scratch with an idea originally created in the product development department and developing it into a game product with the help of the designers in the product development team. The stages of a game design process and the questions the designer needs to ask are usually the following:

Table 1. Stages in the board game development process.

Steps in the board game design process	Questions
1. Coming up with a game idea	Is this an interesting idea – does it have novelty value?
2. Designing the game mechanics	Do the mechanics work, are they easily understandable?
3. Writing the game rules	Are the rules simple and clear enough?
4. Designing the components (game parts)	Are the components visually and tactually well designed? Are they economical to produce?
5. Visualizing the materials for the game (board, components, rules sheet)	Are the materials aesthetically pleasing? Does the player understand their function?
6. Designing the packaging materials and visual look	Does the look of the game package communicate its idea efficiently? Is it captivating on the shelf among other games?
7. Making the prototype	Do the game elements work together?
8. Testing the game with the right target group	How is the game experienced? Is it fun, joyful, exciting, challenging enough?
9. Making final adjustments to the prototype	What are the flaws that need to be corrected?
10. Offering the game idea to a publisher	Are there any similar games on the market or back to nr. 1: does it have novelty value?

To design games at a publishing house means to work in a team. Practically, in a game publisher's process the steps of product development include 1) coming up with ideas for games (often through brainstorming), 2) selecting the best ideas, 3) making the publishing decisions, 4) developing the ideas into ready made games, and 5) planning the marketing and advertising for these games together with other team members and departments.

The development of ideas into actual games involves decisions about what kind of components, visuality and rules the game will include. Since the game designers are the experts on the contents of the game, they are actively involved in planning the means of marketing to be used in promoting the games. Also, at a publishing house, the game designers assist in producing textual marketing material for the games to catalogues, printed promotion material, advertisements and the company's web pages on Internet.

The number of game ideas flowing to the publisher is much larger than the amount of games that can be commercialized during one year. Game publishing, just as book publishing, is a form of business that is reliant on the ability to see, and to distinguish the meaningful from the meaningless. Thus, a publisher – also in the area of games – can be seen as a gatekeeper, an exerciser of cultural power.

7. Learning to play the design game

The qualitative interviews conducted for this study in January 2009 were carried out with five game design professionals at a Scandinavian game publishing company. All the interviewees have worked 4 or fewer years for the company and none of them have an education directly having to do with game design. The designers working with packaging design, visualizing and modeling the game parts (such as game board, playing pieces etc.) are trained as graphic designers in open colleges and design schools. The game developer and head of department have their educational background in university studies mainly in the humanistic sciences.

The interviewees represented the following roles in the product development (game design) team: Graphic designers (3), game developer (creates and develops game ideas and mechanics, 1), head of department (1). Apart from the designers interviewed, the department employs a text coordinator (editing texts and translations for games) and a number of freelance (graphic) designers who were excluded from this study. All designers have played games in their childhood and now play regularly new games in order to learn more about current gaming trends. No one, except the designer whose task is mainly to develop the mechanics of the game further (game developer), evaluated himself or herself as a passionate player of games. However, having started in the current position as a member of the product development team at a game publishing company, has increased the interest towards playing both digital and traditional games.

7.1 Getting started: The elements of inspiration

Designing a game starts with an idea. Once an idea about the mechanism or theme is considered as something worth developing further, the actual design process begins. Visual and thematic inspiration to game design projects is looked for in other media; literature, television and film. What inspires game designers is that games are always different from another. The working environment, the internet and books all bring inspiration. I.e. when designing a pirate themed game a pirate book including images from the history of pirates may be used as an inspirational starting point for design work. The fashion industry and other areas of business, mainly regarding packaging design, offer new ideas. Also the world of games itself is considered as a source of inspiration. Very small details in the debriefing might help the way ideas start to develop. The inspirational work might also be

guided by practical matters such as what colours have not been used in the game boxes in the past years, if there is a trend colour that everyone is using at the moment that is interesting etc.

All visual stimuli such as news and movies and everything in between, both in printed and digital media help graphic designers to develop visuals for games. The fact that there are no right ways to do game design is also considered inspirational. There are many different elements involved in making the game such as writing the texts, planning the physical appearance, ensuring profitability and taking in consideration international audience. The almost endless possibilities and challenging nature of the design work makes game design a particularly interesting form of industrial design.

7.2 Working on it: Designer likes and dislikes

The most rewarding tasks mentioned in the interviews is coming up with new ideas for games (thematic and mechanical) and designing the graphics for game boxes and parts. The least favourite task in game designing is considered to be the further development of a colleagues design work, in other words finalizing and editing tasks having to do with packaging design and text lay out. Also, to question what the game to be designed is about in terms of game play and theme inspires the designers to begin a new project. Starting the design work for a new board game often begins with the question what the game in question wants to communicate to the end-users, that is, the players. The design work for any game requires the designer to provide an answer to this particular question.

7.3 Game of know-how: Fellow designers as knowledge providers

As none of the members of the product development team of the game publisher under scrutiny have an education specifically concentrating on game design, the principals have been taught mainly at the game publishing house by colleagues and superiors, even by people in managerial positions. The importance of the expertise of fellow team members as teachers of practical and tacit knowledge is stressed in the process of designers learning from one another. The publishing company provides the designers with skills that could not be communicated and learnt even through game design education. Such skills include i.e. the use of business mathematics specially tied to the area of board games that the management communicates to the designers.

7.4 Learning by oneself: Independent studies as a source for insight

The interviews show that independent studies in the field of games and packaging design contribute to the know-how of game designers. Reading guide books, visiting trade fairs and own analyses of games published by other companies give valuable insight. Additionally, designers may benefit from game related childhood interests and activities as described by one designer: "I have had computer games as a hobby. Studying and knowing about 3D graphics has entered the picture because of that. In my childhood when I was playing games with my friends we came up with our own rules and drew our own graphics. I also remember to have designed a game of my own. Playing this game was not relevant but designing it was fun." Reading game design related literature and professional magazines, visiting trade fairs, looking at competitors products and studying board game related sites on the Internet also provide a source of insight for the game designer. Toy design and altogether all sort of

packaging design, such as packaging of cosmetic products are areas of design that offer ideas and learning opportunities in the work of a board game designer.

7.5 Design rules defined: Design philosophy as tacit knowledge

Understanding the company design philosophy may be seen as tacit knowledge as the guidelines may only be given in spoken word and passed between the colleagues inside the product development team. According to the interviewees the design philosophy is dictated by moral and ethical values, sustainability and commercial thinking. As the possibilities do design game visuals are almost endless, it is considered important that the design does not upset anyone. Family oriented visuals are important as the products designed are meant for a wide audience – the mass market. A game designer formulates: “I think that the market dictates what we do, but again, we offer what the masses think they want”.

7.6 Tacit game design skills are passed on

“I’m sure there are some things that need to be shown and cannot be told in words”. This comment made by one of the interviewees summarizes well the character of tacit game design skills. As stated by Gourlay, tacit knowledge is a non-linguistic non-numerical form of knowledge that is highly personal and context specific and deeply rooted in individual experiences, ideas, values and emotions [16]. The role of tacit knowledge is understood as an important part of the learning process in game design. The lack of accurate education and guidelines challenges the designers to build up the know-how through learning by doing and analyzing past projects, as illustrated in the following quote: “In this kind of a small company there is more tacit than formal knowledge. With formal knowledge I mean the practices that have been negotiated. Everything I can do with the computer is tacit knowledge – it’s not something that is outlined or could easily be handed out someone else. Other kind of tacit knowledge may also be used as a powerful means for example to ask, how different machines in the production work, has helped me to understand better. Especially in this field where there is no education almost all the information we have is tacit. You just have to dig it from somewhere. There is a lot of it.”

There is not very much written information - knowledge passed on through everyday communication plays an important role. The designers acquire and improve their board design skills through spending time in the game business, by discussing successes and failures. The members of the product development team make a web where bits of information travel back and forth to other colleagues.

7.7 Building blocks of play value acknowledged

The question of play value is considered important. Fun, excitement, learning, challenge, smooth game play and nicely designed visual material are all considered as factors not to be foreseen besides safety and durability aspects. It is a very common thought that game designers design what they like themselves. On the contrary, what designers need to do is to try to understand the thoughts of the end-user – the player. The multicultural gaming audience of the game publisher means that cultural matters have to be addressed in both visual and verbal design work. Localizing the products creates a great amount of work, for example in the different language versions of

games. But it also creates significant added value. Language plays a significant role for a person's identity and when a game is available in the customer's own language, it will be more readily purchased by that customer. Games are considered from the viewpoint of the experience delivered. Different board games should deliver different gaming experiences related i.e. with fun, excitement, mathematical challenge. How well the designer is able to communicate the experience is key, as well as a smoothness related to the mechanics and flow of a game.

7.8 Designing for all: Internationality influences design work

As seen, the multicultural audience for games published by an international company affects the design work in terms of graphics, language and cultural preferences. Acknowledging what can and what cannot be used in game design in different cultures forms an area of tacit knowledge that can only be learnt through experience. Even small details are important as the interviews show: Something having to do with language cannot necessarily be used in one country if the game is adapted to another language. One cannot design just on base of a language as this restricts the design. For example a door knob may look different in one country compared to another. When the aim is to produce a universal product that can be sold to as many markets as possible, compromising is needed. Localized games take target group and local culture more closely into consideration, but at the same time, they create a heavier workload for the designers. The different cultures should be honored as different images and signs trigger different reactions in cultures and their people.

7.9 Informative discussions as design guidance

The 'right' design for a game depends on its target group and qualities. Often, the sales people have their say in what is considered as good design work. The head of the product development department says: "Sometimes the feedback comes in written and sometimes just in spoken communication. In every single person lives a little designer and the opinions differ from another. There is a challenge to see what 'right design' is".

Information regarding designs for games in different phases of the development process most often comes through the sales department and flows from the head of the design department on to the product development team. The wishes coming from the sales people are sometimes considered vague and criticized by the designers. Support from other designers and discussions inside the team are claimed in order to reach a better understanding of what is needed design-wise. Feedback regarding design issues does not very often come directly from consumers, but from other informants such as buyers. Internal product development meetings give the designers a possibility to discuss topics raised by these. The information distilled from the sales department is not considered the best way to learn how things should be taken further. Discussions with all the people involved with the game products are needed - be it the designer, production or sales people.

7.10 Indirect feedback indicates directions

As illustrated, feedback from buyers and end-users come through the sales department and international subsidiaries, sometimes end-users communicate their thoughts about games directly to the product development team through mail and e-mail. Game playing sessions with test groups also provide the designers with information

about reactions on game mechanics and visual aspects: End-users give feedback in situations of two kinds: at consumer fairs and criticism through internet. Positive feedback from end-users is rarely communicated directly to game designers. At consumer and trade fairs the participating designers have the opportunity to see how much people enjoy playing the games.

7.11 Improving the design performance

Improving design skills has to do with the designer's individual abilities. In a constantly changing environment and new game products to design, the designers meet with new situations that require knowledge that has to be learned from scratch. Information regarding technical aspects can be acquired through active discussion with other departments such as the production, as one graphic designer explains: "Person X from our production just explained me in which way the cardboard printed game markers are best removed from their frame. Technical information sips from the production and in many occasions you may get information about something that has necessarily not even reached the head of the production. But you cannot start asking everything from everyone."

Know-how about game mechanics is gained through discussing the game play with the original inventor of the idea or the game developer. There is a need from game designers new to their task to gain an analytical understanding of the game; when a game is good and when it's not - what are the mechanics that create the functionality of a game. Sometimes communicating an idea in ones head through a drawing may even be considered hard: "An idea does not necessarily look as good on paper as it is in your own mind".

8. Conclusions: Learning to design play

The objective of this article was to clarify how the principles of game design are learnt by designers working at a product development team in a game publishing company. First, I described games and their design process in its various stages in theory. Secondly, some aspects of game design were further addressed through a description of the practical tasks included. Learning to design play can be seen as a complex process including not just theoretical knowledge, but even more importantly, tacit skills. Tacit knowledge about game design is according to this study acquired through active communication with fellow designers in the product development team and information passed on by other departments such as the sales and production departments and the company management. The diversity of the educational backgrounds seems to enrich the design team as a whole as a game may have its thematic origin in any area possible. Also, as different skills are exposed to designers through their colleagues, the working environment becomes a unique learning place.

Independent studies in the areas of games, packaging design and the field of visual culture in general support and give inspiration to the design work. The international audience of the game products designed means that attention needs to be paid into cultural issues. Multicultural design not only provides challenges, but adds interest to the projects. The creation of play value is considered crucial. The publishing company indicates certain values that the end-products should communicate such as ethics and good manners. Ultimately, it is the designers' task to define the building blocks of play value through their expertise. As stated by one of the designers: "A good game has to

create excitement and joy. When you are playing it you should feel like little butterflies in your stomach but you should also be able to laugh.” Fun, excitement, joy and challenge are defined as creators of play value.

In the end it is a matter up to the designers to decide how these elements of the play experience are communicated to the end-users or players of the games. A deeper analysis and formulation of the board game experience could offer an interesting follow-up to this study. In this way the tacit knowledge could be decoded into more concrete information that would benefit the work at a board game publishing company. In the light of this article, my conclusion is that expertise in game design means mastering a multitask challenge which may best be learned through familiarizing oneself with both tacit knowledge learned in everyday work but also by analyzing feedback coming from different directions: other designers, the management, salespeople, customers and most importantly the end-users who are the players of the games – the ones indicating whether or not the game designers have been able to create good play value – a great gaming experience.

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APPENDIX A.: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Occupation:

Age:

Number of years in the company:

Education:

1. Relationship towards games and playing games before and during this occupation?
2. Most usual task in publishing house having to do with game design?
3. Favourite / least favourite design task?
4. View / your definition on company game design philosophy?
5. Your own game design philosophy (what is crucial in a good game, creates play value)?
6. Who has taught you about game design in the company?
7. Have you learned some things about game design on your own (how, where)?
8. How does the multicultural audience for the game products affect your design work?
9. How do you receive feedback: inside product development, from sales, from management, from customers, from end-users?
10. In which ways is information regarding design issues communicated?
11. In which ways is tacit knowledge communicated- do you have tacit skills?
12. What kind of new game design skills do you think would be good to improve in the future?
13. What inspires you in your design task?